

HYDROTHERMAL SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MOLYBDENUM DISULFIDE NANOSHEETS

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports the hydrothermal synthesis of molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) nanosheets. The few-layered nanosheets have a potential due to their two-dimensional structure and electronic properties, making them good candidates for various applications, including nanofiltration membranes, energy storage, and sensing. A simple hydrothermal synthesis method has been used to prepare these nanosheets, involving the reaction of molybdenum and sulfur sources at higher temperatures. To know the synthesized nanosheets, we have used powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) material characterization techniques to confirm the successful synthesis of MoS₂ nanosheets.

Keywords: MoS₂, Nanosheets, Hydrothermal Synthesis, XRD, FT-IR, TEM

1. INTRODUCTION

Molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) is a part of the transition metal dichalcogenide (TMD) family. MoS₂ is a two-dimensional layered structure nanomaterial that exhibits excellent electronic, optical, and catalytic properties [1,2]. Due to these characteristics, MoS₂ nanosheets are suitable for applications in energy storage, catalysis, and electronic devices [3,4]. Using the hydrothermal

synthesis method, we have synthesized MoS₂ nanosheets with several advantages, including simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and morphological control [5,6]. In this synthesis approach, the reaction of molybdenum and sulfur precursors takes place in a sealed autoclave under high temperatures, leading to the formation of MoS₂ with diverse morphologies, such as nanoflowers, nanoflakes, and nanosheets [7,8]. The properties of hydrothermally synthesized MoS₂ nanosheets depend directly on the synthesis parameters, including the choice of molybdenum and sulfur precursors, temperature, and reaction time [9,10]. By adjusting these parameters, different morphologies can be achieved, ranging from tube-like spheres to thread clusters and spongy, cotton-like structures [11,12]. To analyze the crystalline structure and morphology of the synthesized MoS₂ nanosheets, we have used characterization techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) [13,14]. Hydrothermally synthesized MoS₂ nanosheets have potential applications in various fields, including supercapacitors, filtration membranes, energy storage, and catalysis [15,16].

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Reagents & Chemicals

Thiourea (purified, NH₂.CS.NH₂) was sourced from Molychem (product code: 19500), and ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate ((NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O, 99%) was also obtained from Molychem (product code: 12160). Both chemicals were supplied by Molychem, Mumbai, Maharashtra 400002, India. All chemical compounds were of analytical grade and utilized without further modifications. We used deionized (DI) water throughout the experiment.

2.2 Synthesis of MoS₂ Nanosheets

The synthesis process of MoS₂ nanosheets is schematically illustrated in Figure 1. The nanosheets were prepared using a hydrothermal method as described in [17]. Specifically, 1.06 g of ammonium heptamolybdate ((NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O) and 1.83 g of thiourea (CH₄N₂S) were completely dissolved in 60 mL of deionized water at room temperature under continuous stirring. The resulting solution was then transferred to a 100 mL Teflon-lined autoclave and heated at 180°C for 16 hours. After the reaction, the autoclave was cooled to room temperature, and the resulting black product was washed several times with distilled water. The products were dried at 80°C for 12 h.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the synthesis of MoS₂ nanosheets

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To study of structural, vibrational, and chemical properties of MoS₂ nanosheets we have used X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, and Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy characterizing techniques. The powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies were carried out to analyze the crystal structure of the MoS₂ nanosheets as a function of the processing conditions as shown in Figure 2. With an XRD pattern indexed at 14°, 33°, and 58° that correspond to the (002), (100), and (110) crystal planes of the MoS₂ structure, MoS₂ nanosheets demonstrate the crystallite nature of MoS₂ materials and are compatible with the relevant standard card (JCPDS card number 371492). No other phases or peaks of impurities were detected. [18,19]. The (002) peak intensity drops and peak broadening happens as a result of smaller crystallites in few-layer or monolayer MoS₂, suggesting exfoliation into thinner layers [20,21]. The detection of two distinct vibrational modes the in-plane E_{12g} mode at approximately 380 cm⁻¹ and the out-of-plane A_{1g} mode at around 405 cm⁻¹ provides evidence of the material's defined lattice structure and intrinsic phonon dynamics. Raman spectroscopy further validates the properties of nanosheets as shown in Figure 3. The frequency difference (Δ) between these peaks serves as a crucial gauge of layer thickness. Because of stacking effects and interlayer interactions, Δ is around 18–20 cm⁻¹ for monolayer MoS₂ and ~25 cm⁻¹ for bulk MoS₂ [22,23]. Additionally, we have employed Raman analysis to investigate the defects, strain, and doping effects in MoS₂ nanosheets. The characterization technique FT-IR spectroscopy as shown in Figure 4 then confirms these findings by revealing broad absorption bands at approximately 480 cm⁻¹, 900 cm⁻¹, 1100 cm⁻¹, and 1650 cm⁻¹. The 900 cm⁻¹ band is attributed to S–S stretching, while the 480 cm⁻¹ band is attributed to Mo–S vibrations [24, 25]. The absorption region between 1100 cm⁻¹ and 1650 cm⁻¹ is connected with hydroxyl and Mo–O vibrations, suggesting partial oxidation or interactions with adsorbed water molecules [26,27]. Notably, the characteristic hydroxyl stretching band at ~3500 cm⁻¹ is absent in the nanosheet sample, implying reduced hydroxyl functionalization or removal of surface-bound water during synthesis or processing [28,29]. By combining these methods, we are able to gain a

thorough understanding of the structure and chemistry of MoS₂ nanosheets. It validates their surface chemistry, layer thickness, phase purity, and crystallinity.

Figure 2: XRD patterns of MoS₂, **Figure 3:** Raman spectra of MoS₂, **Figure 4:** FT-IR spectra of MoS₂

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) study of the MoS₂ nanosheets made with ammonium heptamolybdate and thiourea revealed a multilayered structure with a homogeneous particle size distribution and well-defined shape [30,31]. The structural integrity of the nanosheets is demonstrated by TEM images taken at various magnifications (Figures 5(a), 5(b), and 5(c)), which emphasize their regulated size and form [32,33]. Furthermore, high-resolution TEM pictures (Figures 5(d), 5(e), and 5(f)) show that the thickness of the nanosheets ranges between 10 and 50 nm, while their edge lengths are adjustable within the nanometer range, usually from 40 nm to several tens of nanometers [34,35]. These results are in line with earlier research that used chemical precursors and ideal reaction conditions to produce MoS₂ nanosheets with regulated synthesis and uniform shape [36, 37]. Nanosheets can be used in energy storage, optoelectronic devices, and catalysis because of their precise controllable dimensions [38, 39].

Figure 5: TEM images of MoS₂ nanosheets.: ((a), (b), (c), (d), (e), and (f))

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, we successfully synthesized MoS₂ nanosheets using the hydrothermal method. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), Raman spectroscopy and FT-IR characterization techniques collectively confirm the crystalline structure, layered morphology, and vibrational properties of the synthesized MoS₂ nanosheets. Due to its simplicity and scalability, the hydrothermal method is ideal for producing MoS₂ nanosheets for energy and electronic applications. Further refinement of synthesis conditions can enhance their structural and functional properties for targeted use.

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